

JOIN MÖBIUS COMMUNITY

Möbius aims to build a **network of ecosystem-related projects** in order to forge synergies.

We strongly believe that **working together** makes it possible to facilitate the integration of emerging technologies, to help **the new media ecosystem** become more adaptive and inclusive, and better promote content; and, support synergies across media, operators, technologists, and cultural/arts actors in order to develop a stronger network of stakeholders.

What can we offer you?

Communication

Share your activities with our European network of stakeholders.

Visibility

Have your logo, website and social media channels on our website as member of our community.

Exclusivity

Participate in our owned activities exclusively as community members.

Discover more at mobius-project.eu/open-call

@mobius_europe

JOIN MÖBIUS COMMUNITY

What do we ask for in return?

Communication

Spread the news of our call, events and articles through your social media channels and newsletters.

Visibility

Include our logo on your website, as one of your collaborators or include it on your social media channels and newsletters.

Boost

Encourage your community to discover and support the Möbius initiative.

Are you ready to join us?

mobius-project.eu/community

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#mobiusbook